

Problems of Irrigation in Maharashtra

Smt. Ashwini Raghunath Kadam¹ and Dr. A. K. Patil²

¹Research Student, Department of Economics, Shivaji University, Kolhapur 416004 Maharashtra, India

²Professor and Head, Department of Economics, SGM College, (Autonomous) Karad 415124 Maharashtra, India

Corresponding author E-mail: ashwinidhamale19jan@gmail.com; ¹ akpatilpune@sgm.edu.in²

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Abstract

Although the state of Maharashtra is considered an advanced state, it lags in behind terms of agriculture. According to the report of Maharashtra Water and Irrigation Commission 225 lakhs of the state's total land area may be utilized for agricultural purposes and the combined potential for irrigation it can happen 126 lakh hectares. However, 74.500 lakh hectares of new irrigation capacity have been created till 30 June 2019. This is the irrigation status in Maharashtra. There is still need for irrigation development in Maharashtra, despite the state having achieved notable advancements in this area. Also, agriculture irrigation in Maharashtra faces many problems. However, the amount of land under irrigation is low in some parts of the state due to inadequate irrigation infrastructure. To extend the state's irrigated land, an appropriate strategy must be developed According to this perspective, it's important to understand Maharashtra's irrigation issues and their remedies.

Keywords: Agricultural Irrigation in Maharashtra, Department of Water Resources, Irrigation Capacity, water conservation.

Introduction

Water is a valuable natural resource, and it's been argued that life depends on it. Planning for and conserving water storage has become crucial in light of this. Earth's water resources are naturally distributed unevenly, both globally and within our continent. Maharashtra is in a similar scenario. There is less water available for agricultural cultivation due to population growth and industrial advancement. As a result, Maharashtra's farmers and agriculture are facing several issues. The state government has implemented several initiatives since independence to build irrigation infrastructure both nationally and within the state. About 80% of people living in rural areas still rely on agriculture for their primary source of income. and it employs roughly 55% of the state's labour and serves as the food supply for an expanding urban population. Given that the state is located in a semi-arid region, irrigation is essential to guaranteeing increased crop output.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the main objectives of the present research work.

1. To study the status of Agricultural Irrigation in Maharashtra.
2. To analyze the problems and measures of agriculture irrigation in Maharashtra.

Research Methodology

The secondary data used in this study was gathered from a variety of sources, including websites, research papers, and the Water Resources Department, the Indian government, the Irrigation Status Indicator Report 2021–2022.

Present Status of Irrigation in Maharashtra

Maharashtra had 3778 projects with partial and full irrigation capacity as of June 30, 2021. These projects were divided into 86 big, 298 medium, and 3394 minor projects. The total irrigation capacity of the state's soil and water conservation departments as of June 30, 2021, and water resources as of April 1, 2021, was 74.559 lakh hectares. The state's estimated amount of usable water storage for 2021–2022 was 43 thousand 469.868 million cubic meters. The available water storage at the end of the Kharif season was 34443.089 One million cubic meters. The total water consumption in the year 2021-22 is 33149.994 One million cubic meters has been consumed. while 19866.645 million were utilized for irrigation. The total amount of water utilized for non-irrigation was 6362.152 million cubic meters. The cost of transportation of one million cubic meters (in the river) was 1696.656 million cubic meters. In non-irrigation water use, 4961.662 One million cubic meters for drinking, 947.953 One million cubic meters for industrial purposes, and 452.537 One million cubic meters for other purposes have been used. In 2021–2022, the state's total irrigated area was 42.113 lakh hectares. 9.981 lakh hectares under small projects, 5.836 lakh hectares under medium projects, and 26.296 lakh hectares under major projects) By the end of June 30, 2021, 54.955 lakh hectares of the 77.228 lakh hectares of projected irrigation capacity had been constructed in the state. In 2021, the State's major crops were: sorghum (3.329 lakhs), wheat (3.914 lakhs), groundnuts (1.105 lakhs), gram (2.725 lakhs), rice (4.718 lakhs), oilseeds (1.602 lakhs), sugarcane (7.658 lakhs), cotton (1.312 lakhs), fruit cultivation (1.666 lakhs), and others (14.084 lakhs). 42.113 lakh hectares were the area. The state would collect Rs. 101.76 crores in irrigation water taxes in 2021–2022. The total collection was Rs.1160.12 crore, of which Rs 1058.36 crore came from the non-irrigation watershed. The amount spent for maintenance and repairs came to Rs. 1308.99 crores.

Table. No. 1: District-wise geographical area, cultivable area, Created Irrigation Capacity (State Level) as of 30 June 2021 and Irrigated Area in 2021-22 (thousand hectares)

Sr. No	District	Geographical area	Cultivable area	Created Irrigation capacity of 30 June 2021	Irrigated Area in 2021-22	Percentage of Created irrigated capacity to cultivable area
1	Mumbai					
2	Mumbai Suburbs	38	0	0.000	0.000	0.00
3	Thane			20.384	10.712	6.27
4	Palghar	934	325	31.484	15.003	9.69
5	Raigad	687	309	23.780	11.951	7.70
6	Ratnagiri	816	556	32.735	7.416	5.89
7	Sindhudurg	504	349	19.943	10.557	5.71
8	Nashik	1563	1012	228.932	178.838	22.62

9	Dhule	733	457	101.389	44.491	22.19
10	Nandurbar	705	305	76.658	19.147	25.13
11	Jalgaon	1164	873	239.249	161.839	27.41
12	Ahmednagar	1702	1360	367.535	379.442	27.02
13	Pune	1562	988	432.295	614.201	43.75
14	Solapur	1488	1325	523.553	446.895	39.51
15	Satara	1058	679	259.017	308.726	38.15
16	Sangli	861	716	368.329	252.790	51.44
17	Kolhapur	777	506	243.663	234.492	48.15
18	Aurangabad	1008	807	136.962	133.928	16.97
19	Jalana	773	715	98.115	60.582	13.72
20	Beed	1069	955	186.504	77.443	19.53
21	Latur	716	650	120.220	56.319	18.50
22	Usmanabad	749	698	144.907	66.290	20.76
23	Nanded	1033	830	224.515	129.264	27.05
24	Parbhani	631	575	219.310	104.251	38.14
25	Hingoli	466	398	56.018	56.691	14.07
26	Buldhana	967	736	107.710	64.998	14.63
27	Akola	543	451	62.130	41.566	13.78
28	Washim	513	407	47.268	31.271	11.61
29	Amravati	1222	814	128.858	94.604	15.83
30	Yavatmal	1352	953	187.712	97.958	19.70
31	Vardha	629	473	141.895	73.385	30.00
32	Nagpur	986	639	186.214	138.402	29.14
33	Bhandara	342	202	156.287	91.370	77.37
34	Gondia	586	215	119.467	80.562	55.57
35	Chandrapur	1092	530	162.244	88.133	30.61
36	Gadhchiroli	1492	254	40.203	27.794	15.83
	Maharashtra	30761	21062	5495.485	4211.311	26.09

Source: Irrigation Status Indicator Report 2021-22

The above table shows the district-wise geographical area, cultivable area, irrigated potential, irrigated area and created irrigated potential as a percentage of cultivable area. The total geographical area of 36 districts in the state is 30761 thousand hectares while the cultivable area is 21062 thousand hectares. As on 30 June 2021, the created irrigation potential in Maharashtra is 5495.485 thousand hectares, while the irrigated area in 2021-22 is 4211.311 thousand hectares. Also, the percentage of the created irrigation potential in the state to the cultivable areas is 26.09 thousand hectares. Thus, the above table shows the status of agricultural irrigation in Maharashtra.

Challenges and Issues in Maharashtra's Development of Irrigation

It is concerning that almost 60% of the total planted area still depends on precipitation despite significant investment in and expansion of irrigation infrastructure. Numerous problems with agricultural irrigation as follow:

Unequal rainfall distribution

India averages 1000 mm of rain on average, whereas Maharashtra averages 1300 mm. Of this, the Sahyadri mountain range, the Konkan, and Vidarbha receive relatively more rainfall, while Madhya Maharashtra, Marathwada, and West Maharashtra receive much less than the average. This leads to limitations

on the water supply, which are detrimental to the growth of the local agricultural industry as well as the region's general economic development.

In water run-off is high

The monsoon season in Maharashtra typically lasts from June to October. Vidarbha and the Konkan area receive the most rainfall. Because of Konkan's unique geological structure, very little water percolates through the soil and there are limits to the construction of projects by building dams in this area. As a result, during the monsoon, the water from the region's rivers flows into the sea. Irrigation of crops is not done using this water. This situation is more or less seen in the case of rainwater falling in other parts of Maharashtra.

Uncontrolled groundwater withdrawal

Groundwater is being taken out on a massive scale in order to mitigate the irregularities of the monsoon, maximize the area under irrigation for agriculture, as well as to acquire drinking water. Thus, the subsurface water level is rapidly dropping every day. Subsurface water sources are being used less for irrigation as a result.

Decrease in area under forest

The area covered by forests in Maharashtra has significantly decreased as a result of widespread deforestation carried out to create space for a variety of economic development initiatives, the construction of industries, the construction of residential buildings, and many other uses. So, rainwater flows without permeation into the ground. In addition, there is a significant quantity of soil erosion. The groundwater table is dropping as a result, which has an impact on irrigation.

Obstacles in building new irrigation projects

To supply irrigation to all of Maharashtra's agricultural land, additional big, medium, and small irrigation projects must be established. The primary concern is how to increase irrigation facilities in the state because it is difficult to acquire the land needed for such projects due to farmer opposition, challenges in providing suitable land for the project, environmental issues, water availability, rising project costs, etc.

Traditional irrigation methods

Almost the majority of Maharashtra uses Traditional irrigation systems for agricultural irrigation. Crop yield is decreased by improper irrigation, and the salt of the soil causes the land to become barren. This technique wastes tremendous water since it irrigates a small amount of land. This raises production costs and restricts agricultural irrigation.

Reduced water availability for irrigation in agriculture

Due to growing industrialization and urbanization, the majority of water resources has reserved for urban areas and industries. In addition, water is used for recreation, water transportation, and power generation. Water for agricultural irrigation is being reduced as a result of the absence of a separate water supply for the city and industry.

Water pollution

Surface and groundwater contamination is a major result of growing industry and urbanization, as well as chemical pesticides and fertilizers used in agriculture. Rivers aren't as pure now. Without any sort of treatment, toxic industrial and urban wastewater are dumped into rivers. There is little to no utility of such contaminated water for farming. A farm's land will soon become salinized and ultimately unusable if tainted water is utilized for irrigation. This leads to issues with the irrigation system for agriculture.

Unrestrained sand extraction

The need for sand for public and residential structures, dams, bridges, highways, and other constructions is rising daily due to factors including population growth, extensive economic development

projects, urbanization, and improved living standards. Uncontrolled extraction of sand, a valuable mineral found in Maharashtra's rivers, is being done in an attempt to get wealthy as quickly as possible. However, the rivers' water levels have deepened as a result of this unchecked sand mining. The effects of agricultural irrigation have been felt as the rivers have dried up. There is less water available for irrigating agriculture.

Other Reasons

In addition to the issues listed above, there are several other reasons why agricultural irrigation water is continuously declining, including the preservation of historically and traditionally significant water resources and a lack of concern for conservation, excessive water waste, a lack of water literacy, selfish inclinations, the failure of government policies, and a water demand that exceeds supply.

Measures For Agricultural Irrigation in Maharashtra

Considering the above various reasons, it is necessary to take the following measures to increase the irrigation water of agriculture in Maharashtra.

Conservation of water

The ultimate source of groundwater and surface water resources is the monsoon rains, so attention should be paid to how to maximize the storage of rainwater. Also, it is necessary to undertake works like forest floor, village floor, farm floor, forestry dams, refilling of wells, widening and deepening of drains, and removing sediment from old water reservoirs. The participation of people in rural areas is important for this work. For that, people in rural areas should be made aware of the importance of water conservation. Also, people should be made aware of the importance of water conservation in urban areas.

Tree plantation

People have been deforesting large amounts of forest for their purposes for a long time. As a result, rainfall is decreasing daily, the underground water level is dropping, and a large amount of soil is being eroded. To address these issues, a tree planting program can be implemented in public areas. This is where social forestry, or the "one person, one tree" initiative, can be helpful. Youth groups, women's groups, voluntary organizations, and students in rural areas can help plant a large number of trees. At the same time, one way to address this problem is to not cut down trees.

Stopping groundwater extraction

Growing populations, agriculture, and other factors are causing a significant volume of groundwater to be extracted. This has caused the water level below the surface to drop. Thus, to prevent the over-extraction of groundwater, a rigorous remediation strategy and legislation must be put in place.

Removing obstacles to the construction of projects

When building small, medium, and large-scale agricultural irrigation projects, several obstacles must be surmounted. The lengthy and rising expense of project development, coupled with political meddling, has caused several projects in Maharashtra to be postponed. Thus, it is important to take the project manager into confidence and plan rigorously to develop a new project in the shortest amount of time and at the lowest possible cost.

Adoption of modern agriculture irrigation system

In Maharashtra, agricultural irrigation is still done using traditional irrigation methods. Using this technique, the land is irrigated rather than the crops. As a result, the ground becomes infertile, and agricultural production per hectare decreases. So how can we use the water that is available wisely to irrigate a greater area of agriculture while consuming less water? Farmers should utilize water-saving techniques like frost and drip irrigation for this. For that, it is necessary to educate the farmers and convince them about the importance of water. The government has to consider and develop a plan on how to supply for drip irrigation system sets at the most affordable price. The government now provides a subsidy for this, but because it is delayed, farmers would rather avoid using the more advanced irrigation method.

Prevention of water pollution

Due to pollution, the majority of Maharashtra's rivers are contaminated. This is because unprocessed urban waste water and contaminated industrial runoff are dumped straight into rivers, streams, and drains, making the water unfit for human consumption or agriculture. Additionally, the increased use of chemical pesticides and fertilizers in agriculture is contaminating groundwater. Therefore, the current regulations should be severely enforced in this respect and it should be mandatory to cleanse the polluted water before releasing it directly into the natural water sources. Farmers ought to use scientific when applying fertilizers to their crops. To reduce water pollution and aid augment the amount of water available for agricultural irrigation, compost and green manures have to be utilized in lieu of chemical fertilizers.

Stopping Sand Mining

The riverbeds have dried up and the subsurface water level has sharply dropped as a result of unrestricted sand mining. Therefore, stringent action must be taken to put an end to sand mining. Sand smuggling has caused several problems, including corruption, hooliganism, and the black market, to spread throughout Maharashtra. Thus, reducing sand theft will contribute to an increase in the groundwater table.

Conclusion

42.113 lakh hectares of land were under irrigation in Maharashtra in 2021–2022. Small projects cover 9.981 lakh hectares, medium projects cover 5.836 lakh hectares, and big projects cover 26.296 lakh hectares. Of the 77.228 lakh hectares of proposed irrigation capacity, 54.955 lakh hectares have been completed in Maharashtra by June 30, 2021. Although the current status of irrigation in Maharashtra is like this, there is a gap between the irrigation capacity created and the actual use. There is a need for various improvements in irrigation management in terms of production irrigation capacity and utilization. Also, many problems are seen in agriculture irrigation. Efforts are needed from all levels of the society for this. Also, as per the changing times, there are solution plans for irrigation such as reuse of treated water for irrigation, reduction of water pollution of natural water sources, development of methods like drip and frost irrigation to reduce water wastage, etc.

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